

Nonrelativistic Limit of Dirac Equation Equivalent to Third Order Expansion of Relativistic Wave Equations? Part II

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 20 2024

In Part I, we suggested a method which may be used to expand solutions of a differential equation in negative powers (not necessarily integer) of m (rest mass). This is the expansion relevant to a nonrelativistic limit of special relativistic differential equations, with W_0 , e_0 being the Schrodinger equation solutions.

In (1), a modified Schrodinger equation is proposed, which introduces an extra term $a \frac{d}{dt} \text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \text{partial} W(x,t)$, where $W(x,t)$ is the wavefunction and a is of the order $1/(\text{mm})$. Here, we apply the expansion method for this differential equation in the case of a harmonic oscillator. We consider the ground state solution.

Equation of (1)

(1) suggests using a modified Schrodinger equation:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} W = -1/2m \text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \text{partial} W + VW + a \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} \text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \text{partial} W \quad ((1))$$

This equation leads to a probability density: $W^*W + a \text{grad} W \cdot \text{grad} W$ ((2)) which matches the density of a Dirac 4 spinor in the nonrelativistic limit, i.e.

$(W, \sigma \cdot p / 2m W)$, where W is the solution of the Schrodinger equation and $a=1/(4\text{mm})$ in Dirac theory and σ is a vector of 2×2 Pauli matrices. ((2))

For the quantum oscillator, the energy is given in (1) by:

$$E = e_n (\sqrt{1 + (e_n a m)(e_n a m)} - e_n a m) \quad \text{where } e_n = (n + .5) w \quad \text{with } w = \sqrt{k/m} \quad \text{and } m = \text{rest mass} \quad ((3))$$

It is possible to expand in negative powers (not necessarily integers) of m (the rest mass) to obtain:

$$E_0 = (n + .5)w \quad ((4a))$$

$$E_1 = -e_n a m \quad ((4b)) \quad \text{and} \quad E_2 = e_n .5 (e_n a m)(e_n a m) \quad ((4c))$$

Essentially, the extra term, proportional to a , leads to a modified mass, as pointed out in (1). Here, we wish to use a method of expanding E and W in negative powers (not necessarily integers) of m , the rest mass.

Method of Expanding the Energy and Wavefunction in Negative Powers of m Rest Mass

The first step is to assume:

$$E = E_0 + E_1 + E_2 \dots \text{ And } W = W_0 + W_1 + W_2 + \dots \quad ((5))$$

Here E_0 and W_0 correspond to the usual Schrodinger equation solution (no a term). E_1 is a negative power (not necessarily an integer) of m (rest mass) and E_2 is of a higher order of m in the denominator. The same holds for the weights of W_1 , W_2 etc. In general, W_0 , W_1 , W_2 would be linearly independent.

The equation to consider is ((1)). In the first approximation, a goes as $1/(mm)$ and so this term may be dropped, yielding the usual Schrodinger equation, so E_0 and W_0 correspond to this.

The next step is to consider a higher power of m in the denominator. This means considering both E_1 and W_1 . It is not clear at first what powers of m in the denominator these have. One may see, however, that the correction to ((1)) is the term: $a (id/dt) \text{ grad dot grad } W$.

id/dt brings in E and the highest order of this is: e_0

a is of the order of $1/(mm)$

The highest order of W is W_0 .

We consider the ground state of the oscillator, i.e. $W_0 = \exp(-.5 \sqrt{km} \ xx)$ ((6))

Thus, $\text{grad dot grad } W_0$ may create different functional forms, namely:

$$\exp(-d \ xx), \quad b_1 xx \exp(-dxx) \text{ where } d = -.5 \sqrt{km} \quad ((7))$$

We consider the possibility of a $W_1 = bxx \exp(-dxx)$ to offset the $b_1 xx \exp(-dxx)$ term.

This would mean that:

$EW \rightarrow e_0 W_1$, $V(x)W$ yields nothing because VW_0 is part of the Schrodinger equation and

VW_1 is of the form $.5kxx \ bxx \exp(-dxx)$ and so does not play a role in this first approximation

$-1/2m \ d/dx \ d/dx \ W_1$ could yield a term of the form $c_1 \ xx \exp(-dxx)$ and so must be considered

Finally, one has the $b_1 xx \exp(-d_1 xx)$ term from the extra term proportional to "a".

$$-1/2m \ d/dx \ d/dx [bxx \exp(-dxx)] = -1/2m [-4bdxx - 6bdxx] \exp(-dxx) \text{ for terms proportional to } xx \exp(-dxx)$$

Thus: $e_0 b = a e_0 4 d d + b (1/ (2m)) (10 d)$

E_0 goes as $1/\sqrt{m}$, $a e_0 k m$ goes as $1/(m \text{ power } 1.5)$ so b must go as $1/m$
 $b(e_0 - 5d/m) = -4e_0 b = a e_0 4 d d$ so $b = -a m e_0$ ((8))

To see if this is in fact the correct result, one may consider the effective mass of (1):

$$M_{\text{eff}} = m / (1 - 2amE) \quad ((9))$$

The full ground state solution is: $\exp(-.5 \sqrt{k m_{\text{eff}}}) x x$ so one may expand m_{eff} to first order in E , i.e. $E=e_0$. Then, the total wavefunction is to this order is:

$$\exp(-.5 \sqrt{k m}) (1 + a m e_0) x x \text{ which may be expanded to: } \exp(-.5 \sqrt{k m}) x x + \exp(-.5 \sqrt{k m}) a m e_0 x x \quad ((10))$$

Thus, b matches $-a m e_0$.

The next step is to consider terms which go as $W_0 = \exp(-d x x)$ in ((1)). This yields:

$$e_1 W_0 = -1/2m d/dx d/dx (b x x \exp(-d x x)) \text{ (only the piece that goes as } W_0) + a e_0 d d/x d/dx \exp(-d x x) \text{ (only the piece that goes as } W_0.)$$

Then:

$$e_1 W_0 = \{-1/(2m) 2b + a e_0 (-2d)\} W_0 \text{ or}$$

$$e_1 = -b/m - 2a e_0 .5 \sqrt{k m} = -a m e_0 \quad ((11))$$

((11)) is in fact the second expansion term of E , e_0 being the Schrodinger result.

Thus, a negative power series (not necessarily integer powers) in m (rest mass) yields various terms of the wavefunction and the energy. These represent the relativistic corrections to the Schrodinger equation using ((1)) as the modified Schrodinger equation.

One may continue the process discussed above to find the next higher order m in the denominator terms, but the above suffices to describe the procedure, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we introduced some time ago an approach to expand solutions of a relativistic wave equation in terms of negative powers (not necessarily integers) of m , the rest mass. The first term, W_0 and e_0 represent Schrodinger equation results, with subsequent terms describing

relativistic corrections. We applied this in the past to the oscillator and infinite square well potential (see Part I for references).

Here, we start with the modified Schrodinger equation proposed by (1). We apply the power expansion to this equation and show how many obtain W_1 and e_1 for the oscillator ground state, which match the first order expansion of the full solution.

References

1. Wilczek, F. and Yi, Z. Probability of Presence Versus $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ May 8, 2024
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